

StArt - State of the Art through Systematic Review

Title:	CRISPR technology for editing susceptibility genes in plant-pathogen interactions: A systematic review.
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Description:	This is a systematic review on the use of CRISPR-Cas technology for editing susceptibility genes (S-genes) aimed at resistance to biotic stresses in plants, covering the period from 2019 to 2026.
Objectives:	To synthesize recent advances related to the use of CRISPR-Cas technology for editing susceptibility genes, identifying the most exploited genes, editing strategies, and effectiveness in disease resistance.
Main Question:	<p>Q1. Which countries use the CRISPR/Cas technique for resistance to biotic factors?</p> <p>Q2. Which crops were edited using the CRISPR/Cas technique?</p> <p>Q3. What was the biotic stress target for which resistance/tolerance was sought through CRISPR/Cas editing?</p> <p>Q4. Which susceptibility gene is identified, characterized, or modified via CRISPR/Cas in the study?</p> <p>Q5. What delivery method was used to introduce the CRISPR/Cas system components into plant cells?</p> <p>Q6. What methods are used to confirm the efficiency of the CRISPR/Cas technique?</p>

<p>Q7. Which explants are most commonly used for gene editing with CRISPR/Cas?</p> <p>Q8. Which vectors were used to express Cas9 and/or gRNA?</p> <p>Q9. Were pleiotropic effects or undesirable changes observed in the development and agronomic characteristics of the edited plants? Q10. Did gene editing result in increased resistance to the disease? If so, how was it described?</p> <p>Q10. Did gene editing result in increased resistance to the disease? If so, how was it described?</p>	
<p>Keywords: <i>CRISPR/Cas9, Susceptibility genes, Plant disease resistance, Gene knockout, Biotic stress.</i></p>	
<p>Source Selection Criteria: Only scientific articles.</p>	
<p>Studies Languages: Only English.</p>	
<p>Source Search Methods: Papers found in widely available scientific databases.</p>	
<p>Source Engine: Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed Central, Science Direct, Springer, CAPES periodical portal, Google Scholar</p>	
<p>Studies inclusion (I) and exclusion criterias (E):</p>	<p>(I) S Genes Knocked Out via CRISPR; (I) Identification of the S Gene; (I) Study of S Genes; (E) Theses, dissertations, manuals; (E) Review articles; (E) Works not written in English; (E) Works without a clear contribution; (E) Works prior to 2019; (E) Escape the theme.</p>
<p>Studies types definition:</p>	<p>Based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.</p>
<p>Initial studies selection:</p>	<p>Articles that contain in their title, abstract, or keywords terms related to CRISPR/Cas technology (e.g., CRISPR/Cas9, CRISPR in plants), combined with susceptibility genes (e.g., susceptibility genes, S-genes) and gene editing/knockout terms (e.g., knockout, gene inactivation) aimed at resistance to diseases or biotic stresses in plants of agricultural interest.</p>

Studies quality evaluation:	The objectives and criteria of inclusion and exclusion were previously defined, without ambiguity. Exclusions of papers based on the characteristics/sources of the studies were appropriate.
Information Extraction Fields:	The study was conducted in the country where the crop was edited, genes are reported as associated with susceptibility and resistance to pests in plants, methods used to prove the effectiveness of the editing, type of transformation, explant used for transformation, and reports of unusual phenotypic characteristics post-editing.
Results Summarization: In the form of graphs, tables and word cloud.	